

Designing good practice guidelines for a prudent use of antibiotics in the poultry sector in Mozambique

Context

In 2019, the Mozambican Government adopted a multi-sectorial national action plan on antimicrobial resistance (NAP-AMR). In the animal health sector, the plan gives priority to the poultry production sector.

Problem

Little information is available on antimicrobial use and resistance in the Mozambican animal sector. Experts suggest that there is a large misuse of antibiotics (AB) encouraged by an outdated and ineffective regulation. Most farmers have limited access to veterinary drugs, but imports of antibiotics have increased with the growth in poultry production that has doubled in the last 10 years.

Solution

The ROADMAP project in Mozambique is supporting the implementation of the NAP-AMR by:

- **Identifying the socio-technical lock-ins and priority for action** in the vet drugs and poultry sectors,
- **Strengthening a community of stakeholders** with veterinary authorities, professional associations (poultry farmers, drugs sellers, veterinarians) and academia (veterinary and social sciences).

Outcome

As expected outcomes:

1. Knowledge on:

- **Veterinary drugs supply chain:** its functioning and regulation.
- **AB use in poultry production:** quantification of AB use at farm level and drivers of the stakeholders' behaviours.

2. Good practice guidelines and a set of priorities for action in the poultry and the vet drugs sectors co-designed by academic and non-academic partners: CIRAD, University Eduardo Mondlane, Association of the Poultry Farmers of the Maputo Province (ADAM), Veterinary authorities (DNDP-MADER).

3. Training activities for:

- **Veterinary students:** measuring AB use at farm level.
- **Poultry farmers:** field trip and experience exchange with counterparts engaged in reducing AB use in La Reunion.

Practical recommendations

The results of the project can be used in:

- Supporting the implementation of the good practice guidelines among poultry farmers at national level.
- Mobilizing the community of stakeholders for other activities contributing to the NAP-AMR.

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Illustrations & Photos

Illustration 1: Contribution of the ROADMAP Project in Mozambique (in red) to the National Action Plan on AMR, Mozambique (in blue)

Photo 1. Drugs retailing in Maputo Province, 2020 (Photo credit: M.Figuié)

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